

Decision-making in public administration, public finance, and the banking sector during governance reforms, fiscal stress, and uncertainty

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Abstract

This special issue advances the literature by examining the theory and practice of decision-making in public finance and management during governance reforms, fiscal stress, and uncertainty. The four articles provide in-depth empirical and comparative analyses in Slovakia, the United States, and Hungary, offering practical insights for policymakers and public managers confronting fiscal challenges. Collectively, the manuscripts address four interrelated themes: (1) decision-making in public and banking sectors under conditions of fiscal stress; (2) comparative approaches to monitoring municipal fiscal health; (3) the dynamics of governance reforms in diverse institutional and national contexts; and (4) the impact of digital technologies on expenditures, social cohesion, innovation capacity, and competitiveness in settlements and regions. By integrating theoretical frameworks with applied research, this special issue enhances understanding of how the public and banking sectors interpret and respond to fiscal stress, while offering evidence-based guidance for strengthening resilience, accountability, and long-term fiscal sustainability. Looking forward, comparative research and policy experimentation will be essential to deepen insights into wise decision-making under uncertainty.

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Published version of record:

Svenson, F., Ermasova, N., & Pietrzak, P. (2026). Decision-Making in Public Administration, Public Finance, and the Banking Sector During Governance Reforms, Fiscal Stress, and Uncertainty. *Public Finance and Management*, 0(0).

<https://doi.org/10.1177/15239721261439296>

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Introduction

Public administration can be understood as a field deeply connected to the pursuit of community well-being. Within this context, public finance and management offer opportunities to move beyond what Kane and Patapan (2006) describe as the “engineering model” of rationalistic, rule-bound governance, toward an ethos that also values intuition, judgment, and virtuous practice (Svenson et al., 2023). At the same time, empirical research into wisdom reminds us to consider historicity, the ways in which place and geography shape patterns of thought and decision-making (Rooney & McKenna, 2008). Building on this, recent studies reveal significant variation in individuals’ decision-making across countries in the public sector (Svenson et al., 2025). These findings suggest that administrators’ preferences for intuition or deliberation are shaped by cultural and institutional contexts, with important implications for how fiscal stress is interpreted and

addressed. In some settings, deliberation may encourage incremental, rule-bound responses, while in others, intuitive judgment may foster adaptive or innovative solutions (Borins, 2008; Boyne, Gould-Williams, Law, & Walker, 2005).

Decision-making today unfolds under extraordinary pressures. Fiscal stress, governance reform, and overlapping crises - from the COVID-19 pandemic to geopolitical conflict and climate-related disasters - have strained public budgets and institutions, limiting governments' ability to deliver services and invest in infrastructure. Scholars have long debated how governments respond to such stress. Some emphasize bounded rationality and incrementalism, where imperfect information leads to satisficing choices (Simon, 1957; Lindblom, 1959). Others highlight rational, staged responses (Forrester & Spindler, 1990; Levine, 1978; Wolman, 1980, 1983), while still others argue that municipal decision-making resembles the "garbage can" model (Bartle, 1996; Downes & Rocke, 1984; Morgan & Pammer, 1988).

A further stream of research examines conditions that promote innovation, pointing to leadership, institutional capacity, and collaboration (Borins, 2008; Boyne et al., 2005; Crosby & Robbins, 2013; Damanpour & Schneider, 2009; Ermasova & Guzman, 2024a; Guzman & Ermasova, 2023, 2025; Walker, 2008). In parallel, frameworks and indicators have advanced the measurement of fiscal health and early warning systems (Brown, 1993; Brown & Potoski, 2003; Brown, Gordon, & Gorina, 2025; Ermasova & Guzman, 2023, 2024a, 2024b; Gorina, Maher, & Joffe, 2018; Leiser, Wang, & Kargman, 2021; Levine, Rubin, & Wolohojian, 1981; Maher, Oh, & Liao, 2020; Maher et al., 2023; McDonald, 2018). Yet measurement alone cannot explain why some governments navigate crises more successfully than others, underscoring the need for closer study of innovative decision-making under fiscal stress.

This special issue advances that agenda by focusing on the theory and practice of decision-making in public finance and management during periods of reform, stress, and uncertainty. The articles that follow highlight diverse contexts: Slovakia demonstrates how methodological choices shape assessments of municipal financial health; East Cleveland illustrates the consequences of bounded rationality under entrenched fiscal crisis; Hungary showcases innovation through digital and smart settlement development, and Chester, PA; Fairfield, AL; Perla, AR; Detroit, MI; San Bernardino, CA; Stockto, CA; Jefferson County, AL; Central Falls, RI; Prichard, AL; Westfall Township, PA; Vallejo, CA and Gould, AR show that decision-making during bankruptcy differs fundamentally from decision-making under normal fiscal conditions.

Together, these cases provide in-depth analyses and practical insights for policymakers, public managers, and financial professionals.

The first article, “Decision-making and monitoring the fiscal health of municipalities in Slovakia”, focuses on the issue of municipal financial health in Slovakia. The authors identify indicators of municipal financial health across various methodologies applied to eight regional urban centers. This study proposes possible adjustments to the methodology for assessing municipal financial health in Slovakia’s specific conditions. The contribution of the research lies in comparing various existing methodologies to evaluate the financial health of local governments and in expanding the approaches to municipal financial health monitoring by incorporating non-financial indicators that may influence it.

The second article, “Theory and Practice of Decision-Making in State and Local Governments During Fiscal Stress: The Case of East Cleveland,” addresses an important topic: how fiscal stress shaped decision-making processes in the City of East Cleveland, Ohio. East Cleveland’s experience illustrates how small, structurally disadvantaged cities can become trapped in perpetual fiscal emergency, where procedural oversight substitutes for effective governance. This article offers insights into the limitations of oversight frameworks, political accountability, and institutional capacity during financial collapse.

The third article, “Digital Municipalities in Hungary: Examples of Participation and Engagement in the Orbit of the European Union’s Digital Strategies”, examines the social and economic impacts of digital and “smart” settlement development in Hungary. It focuses on the implementation of the European Union’s digital strategies within the framework of national programs such as the Digital Wellbeing Program (DWP) and the Digital Settlement Program (DSP). By analyzing four Hungarian case studies (Nagypáli, Ceglédbercel, Tamási, and the Northern Hegyháti Micro-Regional Union), the authors show that the successful application of digitalization depends largely on community participation, municipal capacity, and institutional stability. Financial analysis reveals that while digitalization initially increases local expenditures, it enhances long-term fiscal efficiency through cost reduction and improved service delivery.

The fourth article, “Decision-Making in Local Governments During Municipal Bankruptcy”, examines how municipalities navigate extreme fiscal crises. Drawing on a multi-case study of twelve municipalities that went bankrupt between 2008 and 2025, it shows that financial collapse rarely stems from a single cause. Instead, it emerges from the interaction of

economic decline, demographic change, fiscal imbalances, institutional constraints, and occasionally governance weaknesses or external shocks. Common pressures include shrinking tax bases, rising debt and pension obligations, legal disputes, and persistent gaps between revenues and expenditures. In these conditions, leaders face severe constraints on autonomy and resources, making urgent decisions under uncertainty and intense political and social pressure. They must balance maintaining services, protecting employment, safeguarding creditors, and restoring fiscal stability - often through difficult measures such as service cuts, labor renegotiations, tax increases, or debt restructuring. The study identifies a clear pattern: initial reactive measures, emergency stabilization, and later structural reforms and institutional restructuring. Some cases highlight failure due to delayed recognition, inadequate monitoring, or overreliance on debt, while others show bankruptcy as a catalyst for stronger financial management, transparency, and sustainable governance. Crises expose weaknesses but also create opportunities for learning, reform, and institutional renewal. Overall, the article offers a compelling analysis of both fiscal failure and the paths to municipal recovery.

The fifth article, “The Fed Funds Risk-Premium after the Silicon Valley Bank Run and the Bank Term Funding Program (BTFP)”, examines the unintended monetary policy effects of the Federal Reserve’s emergency lending facility, the Bank Term Funding Program (BTFP), introduced on March 12, 2023. The study finds that following the failures of Silicon Valley Bank and Signature Bank, a statistically significant risk premium emerged between the federal funds rate and short-term Treasury bills. Specifically, the spread between Fed funds loans and 28-day T-bills increased by approximately 39 to 56 basis points, indicating a shift in money market conditions.

The analysis suggests that the BTFP altered bank incentives by allowing institutions to borrow against high-quality securities at favorable terms. As a result, banks were encouraged to retain Treasury securities and other eligible collateral rather than sell them for liquidity. This behavior contributed to lower Treasury yields and widened spreads in short-term funding markets. The authors argue that these dynamics effectively loosened monetary conditions without an explicit federal funds rate cut, highlighting how crisis-response liquidity facilities can influence market pricing and policy transmission in unintended ways.

Conclusions

This special issue underscores that decision-making in public administration and finance during periods of fiscal stress is neither uniform nor purely technical, but deeply shaped by context, history, and institutional capacity (Rooney & McKenna, 2008; Svenson et al., 2025). The five contributions illustrate this diversity: Slovakia highlights how methodological choices in assessing municipal financial health can alter both diagnosis and response (Brown, 1993; Gorina, Maher, & Joffe, 2018; Maher, Oh, & Liao, 2020); East Cleveland reveals the consequences of bounded rationality and fragile governance under entrenched fiscal crisis (Simon, 1957; Lindblom, 1959; Levine, Rubin, & Wolohojian, 1981; Wolman, 1980, 1986); Hungary demonstrates the potential of innovation through digital transformation and community engagement (Borins, 2008; Boyne et al., 2005), and twelve cases in fourth article illustrates how bankruptcy can serve as a catalyst for institutional renewal, prompting stronger financial management, enhanced transparency, and the adoption of sustainable governance practices (Nelson, 2012; Gorina et al., 2018; Guzman & Ermasova, 2023, 2025). Together, these cases show that wise public decision-making emerges from the interplay of deliberation and intuition, institutional resilience, and sensitivity to place and history (Kane & Patapan, 2006; Svenson et al., 2023). By integrating theoretical perspectives with empirical evidence, the articles advance our understanding of how governments interpret and respond to fiscal stress, offering insights that extend beyond technical measurement to questions of judgment, accountability, and resilience. In doing so, they contribute to broader debates on how public institutions can strengthen their capacity to act wisely in an era of uncertainty and overlapping crises. Looking ahead, comparative research across diverse institutional settings and policy experimentation in fiscal governance will be essential to deepen our understanding of how wisdom can be operationalized in practice.

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